

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON FOLKLORE MATERIALS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the development of speech, the role and importance of folklore in children's education, riddles and proverbs. Riddles are also of particular importance in the proper organization of literary education in primary grades, and in ensuring the spiritual maturity of students. It is noted in the literature on this topic that riddles are masterpieces of centuries-old folk wisdom and are artistic creations that develop human perception, observation, and poetic imagination.

Key words: folklore, folklore, education of young people, speech, speech development, proverbs and riddles.

In our country, the main task of the education system is to educate young people, who are the successors of our future, using innovative, advanced methods and methods, using modern pedagogical technologies, and to increase the quality and efficiency of students in education, to educate young people to be competitive. is considered Speech means the process of speaking and its result. In fact, speech is one of the highest, most complex, spiritual tasks of a person. A specific function of a person that arose as a means of mutual exchange of ideas between people in the process of social work.

There are external and internal, oral and written types of speech. External speech mainly serves the purposes of communication, so it is structured in a way that is understandable to the listeners. The inner speech that is not spoken or written, that is, the speech for itself, is the mind? Self-awareness plays a very important role in thought processes. Written speech (writing and reading letters) is functionally closely related to internal speech (whispering what is to be written inside, reading without making a sound).

It is known that colloquial language is the first guide of speech development, and it gradually improves. Colloquial language is manifested in the oral narration of the read texts. Learning to speak takes place in all lessons, but reading lessons should be of primary importance. Spiritual development of young schoolchildren is embodied through the mother tongue. The mother tongue, including reading, is one of the most important tools in the educational process. Read the practical importance of melodiousness, i.e. reading with recitation, in standardizing students' oral and written speech, ensuring their proportionality, determining the nature and characteristics of the national language, reflecting the laws of expression and pronunciation. it is necessary to observe the norms and standards of the literary language, to search for ways to improve reading methods and to put the most convenient ones into practice.

Riddles are also of particular importance in the proper organization of literary education in primary grades, and in ensuring the spiritual maturity of students. It is noted in the literature on this topic that riddles are masterpieces of centuries-old folk wisdom and are artistic creations that develop human perception, observation, and poetic imagination. They are not only a fun game, a means of spiritual recreation, but also play a key role in knowing the spiritual world and historical past of the ancestors. It would not be correct to consider oral literature, including riddles, as folk entertainment. Each example of folk art is the mind, conscience, fixed spiritual image and historical memory of that nation.

Along with the task of fully mastering reading skills in a modern primary school, the teacher has the task of literary development of schoolchildren. This problem can and should be solved in any study material. In my opinion, folklore material is very valuable.

Proverbs and sayings are the greatest value in enriching the literary language, giving it effectiveness and clarity. There is another division of folklore genres, which depends on the size of the work. So, fairy tales, narratives, epics, historical songs, folk theater belong to major folklore genres, riddles, riddles, matals, and minor genres.

The content of many proverbs serves not only as material for learning grammatical rules, but also as a source of moral virtues: love for nature, Motherland, work, they teach to be kind and sympathetic. Working with proverbs and proverbs in early childhood language and literacy classes is an important part of teaching literacy and is an excellent resource for developing students' thinking and speaking.

Folklore genres studied in primary school are quite common. Each of the genres performs its own function: it provides a folk interpretation of historical events, contains the moral potential necessary for the formation of a person, contains information that expands a person's worldview, and creates the necessary emotional mood. A lot of information about the rich life experience of the people, their moral, , social, family, household, religious views can be found in folklore genres existing in Surhondarya and Kashkadarya region: proverbs, proverbs, riddles, , tales. . "They reflected the wisdom and experience of countless generations of our ancestors, the best qualities and qualities of the character of an Uzbek person in a concentrated form: hard work, kindness, courage, generosity, love for the neighbor, homeland, country. Thus, as a result of the active use of small folklore genres, children's educational and cognitive opportunities increase; children learn to speak more expressively, express their thoughts more deeply, which is reflected in other lessons; entertainment tasks help to develop the logic of children's thinking, spatial imagination, imagination and will, to expand their horizons and general understanding of the world around them.

Conclusions: folklore plays an important role in raising children. Dividing it into genres allows enriching the spiritual world of a child at a certain age, patriotism, respect for the past of one's people, learning its traditions, and learning the norms of moral education and behavior in society. will give.

Folk art develops a child's oral speech, affects his spiritual development and imagination. Each genre of children's folklore teaches certain moral standards. Proverbs and proverbs teach children folk wisdom that has been tested for centuries and has not lost its relevance even in our time. Riddles help young students to develop logical thinking and imagination.

Rapid utterances allow students to overcome speech defects, develop oral speech, and construct logically correct sentences.

With the help of small forms of folklore, almost all problems of speech development methodology can be solved, and it is necessary to use the richest material of folklore.

Thus, we can conclude that introducing a child to folk culture should begin in childhood, because the basic concepts and patterns of behavior are laid at that time. Cultural heritage passes from generation to generation, develops and enriches the child's world.

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